

Reverse Engineering User Stories from Code using Large Language Models

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Instructions

The **GroundTruth_UserStory_Code** folder contains two main directories: **Code_Snippets** and **Reference_Stories**.

- **Code_Snippets**: This directory includes subfolders organized by NLOC ranges. Each subfolder contains the code snippets used in this study, saved as .cpp files.
- **Reference_Stories**: This directory contains CSV files for each NLOC range. Each CSV file includes manually generated user stories corresponding to the code snippets.

The **Prompts** file includes the following types of prompts:

- Zero-shot
- Zero-shot-SCoT
- One-shot
- One-shot -SCoT
- Few-shot
- Few-shot-SCoT

Acronyms:

- NLOC stands for Non Commenting Lines of Code
- SCoT stands for Structure Chain of Thought reasoning

Table1: Benchmark Comparison of LLaMA and GPT Models

Category	Benchmark	LLaMA 3.1 8B	LLaMA 3.1 70B	LLaMA 3.1 405B	GPT-4	GPT-4 Omni	GPT-3.5
Math	GSM8K (5-shot, CoT)	51.9	95.1	96.8	94.2	96.1	96.4
Tool Use	BFCL	76.1	84.8	88.5	80.3	80.5	90.2
Long Context	NIH/Multi-needle	98.8	97.5	98.1	-	100.0	90.8
Multilingual	Multilingual MGSM	68.9	86.9	91.6	85.9	90.5	51.4
Code	MBPP EvalPlus (base)	72.8	88.6	89.6	86.6	87.8	82.0
Code	HumanEval (0-shot)	72.6	80.5	89.0	86.6	90.2	68.0
Pricing (per 1M tokens)		LLaMA 3.1 8B	LLaMA 3.1 70B	LLaMA 3.1 405B	GPT-4	GPT-4 Omni	GPT-3.5
Input		\$0.05	\$0.65	\$9.50	\$30.00	\$2.50	\$3.00
Output		\$0.25	\$2.75	\$9.50	\$60.00	\$10.00	\$4.00

Description:

A comparison between LLAMA models (8B, 70B, and 405B) and GPT models (GPT-4, GPT-4 Omni, and GPT-3.5) across various benchmarks, with bolding the highest-performing model for each benchmark. Additionally, the cost associated with processing 1 million input and output tokens for each model [1]

Table 2: Examples of Generated vs. Ground-Truth User Stories with Corresponding F1 Scores

NLOC	Ground-Truth Story	Generated Story	F1 Score
1–10	As a user, I want to determine the number of digits required for the sum of two numbers, so that I can quickly gauge the magnitude of the sum.	As a user, I want to figure out how many digits the sum of two integers will contain, so that I can quickly gauge the magnitude of the sum.	0.90
91–100	As a user, I want to calculate the circumscribed circle of a triangle, so that I can obtain its center and radius for further geometric analysis.	As a user, I want to compute the triangle’s circumcircle—its center point and radius—directly from its vertices, so that I can obtain this information for further geometric analysis.	0.84
141–150	As a user, I want to determine the K-th smallest product from a list of integers, so that I can identify the specific ranked product for further analysis.	As a user, I want to identify the product that ranks K-th smallest within a list of integer combinations, so that I can identify the specific ranked product for further analysis.	0.85
201–210	As a user, I want to compute the minimal travel path through a selected group of towns, so that I can determine the shortest route and reduce the overall travel cost.	As a user, I want to compute the minimal travel path through a selected group of towns, so that I can plan my journey efficiently and cut down on distance and cost.	0.81
341–450	As a user, I want to calculate the sum of all possible combinations of elements from a set of elements, so that I can efficiently compute the answer modulo a prime number.	As a user, I want to calculate the sum of all possible combinations of elements from a set of elements, so that I can perform advanced modular computations without manual effort.	0.75

Description:

A selection of user story pairs from different NLOC ranges comparing ground-truth stories to those generated by the LLMs, accompanied by their similarity measured using the F1 score. Higher F1 values indicate greater similarity.

References

[1] Llama.com. (n.d.). *Llama: Open and Efficient Foundation Language Models*. Retrieved December 6, 2024, from <https://www.llama.com>